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MANGIFERIN: AN INTERESTING MOLECULE IN NATURE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, herbal drugs are having wide attention in pharmaceutical research due to their cultural acceptability, and safety when compared to synthetic drugs. There are several phytoconstituents which are pharmacologically active. Mangiferin is one among the phytoconstituents with extensive pharmacological action. Mangiferin (MGF) is a secondary metabolite of plants that contains a polyphenol structure. Chemically mangiferin is 1,3,6,7-tetrahydroxyxanthone-C2-β-D-glucoside and it is also a xanthone derivative, that has been reported to occur naturally in several genera. It exhibited a wide range of pharmacological activities, offering a wide possibility to upcoming research fields to explore the drug molecule in clinical application. This review gives the information about source of mangiferin, its chemistry and the various biological activities it possesses.

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INTRODUCTION

Natural drugs have been part of pharmaceuticals formulations for many years.[1] Natural products are less harmful and have fewer adverse effects than synthetic ones. As a result, their application in the treatment of different disorders is growing daily.[2] Because herbal medicines have a wide therapeutic application and few adverse effects, they are always a fantastic source for pharmaceutical research. Due to the well-known negative consequences of synthetic medications, research on phytochemicals has increased during the past few decades. One of the main phytochemical groupings that have had its pharmacological actions thoroughly investigated is flavonoids. These are polyphenol-containing secondary metabolites from plants. Important enzymatic processes are altered by flavonoids, which result in a variety of biological actions. Mangiferin (MGF) is a plant flavonoid that stands out above others due to the vast variety of pharmacological effects it exhibits.[3] Tetrahydroxyxanthone-C2-D-glucoside, also known as mangiferin, is a xanthone derivative that has been reported to occur naturally in a number of taxa.[4] Mangiferin has a wide range of biological activities, including anti-diabetic, anti-depressant, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, neuroprotective, renoprotective, hepatoprotective, dermoprotective, cardio-stimulatory, immune-modulatory, wound healing, anti-hyperlipidemic, bone repair, anti-viral, anti-anxiety, anti-ulcer, and anti-cancer activity.[3] The objective of this review article is to understand various pharmacological activities of indigenously obtained herbal constituent mangiferin.

Figure No:1. Pharmacological activities of mangiferin.

SOURCES OF MANGIFERIN

Mangifera indica (mango tree) remains the main source of mangiferin and mangiferin was first discovered as a colourant component from mango.[5][6] Despite being present in a wide variety of plant species, C-glucosylated xanthones are also found in a few, occasionally distantly related taxa of flowering and cryptogamous plants (ferns).[7] Mangiferin was found in 60 species, 18 genera, and 13 families of dicots, as well as in ferns and monocots, more or less sporadically. The main distribution foci for this compound among these appeared to be the 23 species and three genera of Gentianaceae [8,9], 19 species of Cyclopia [10], and 12 species of Hypericum [11].

Table No:1. Sources of mangiferin.

Species	Family	Plant part	Reference
<i>Mangifera indica</i> , and other species: <i>M. pajang</i> , <i>M. zeylanica</i>	Anacardiaceae	bark, leaves, fruits	[12-14, 15, 16]
<i>Aphloia theiformis</i>	Aphloiaceae	leaves	[17]
<i>Anemarrhena asphodeloides</i>	Asparagaceae	rhizome	[18]
<i>Salacia reticulata</i> , <i>S. chinensis</i> , <i>S. obonga</i>	Celastraceae	roots	[19, 20]
<i>Cyclopia genistoides</i> , <i>C. intermedia</i> , <i>C. subternata</i> , <i>C. maculata</i>	Fabaceae	leaves	[21, 22, 23]
<i>Swertia sp.</i>	Gentianaceae	Aerial parts	[24, 25]
<i>Canscora decussata</i>	Gentianaceae	Whole plant	[26]
<i>Iris domestica</i> (<i>Belamcanda chinensis</i>)	Iridaceae	rhizomes	[27,28]
<i>Bombax malabaricum</i>	Malvaceae	leaves	[29]

CHEMISTRY AND STRUCTURE OF MANGIFERIN

Mangiferin is a xanthone C-glucoside and is also known as 1,3,6,7-tetrahydroxy-2-[3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-2-yl]xanthen-9-one (Figure 2). The term C-glucoside xanthone refers to a polyphenol and bioactive norathyriol derivative to which a glycone component has been added at the norathyriol ring's C-2 position. It consists of a primary glycosidic hydroxyl group, a lactonic carbonyl group, two aromatic rings, one secondary nonaromatic hydroxyl group, and one nonaromatic secondary hydroxyl group. The therapeutic potential of mangiferin is due to these functional groupings.[30]

Mangiferin has a molecular weight of 422.35g, a melting point of 271 °C, and partition coefficient value of -0.693. Its chemical formula is C₁₉H₁₈O₁₁. [1] It is a light-yellow, crystalline powder that is soluble in water, methyl alcohol, and diethyl ether but insoluble in acetone, hexane, and diethyl ether.[31-33] Additionally, it has been shown that mangiferin's solubility declines with rising temperature in the following order: ethanol > methanol > water > diethyl ether > acetone > n-hexane.[34,35] But in DMSO and DMF, it is easily soluble. Mangiferin has absorption maximum at 293 nm using a UV spectroscopic technique.

Chemical structure of mangiferin.

Figure No:2. Chemical Structure of mangiferin.

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF MANGIFERIN

Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, antimicrobial, analgesic and antipyretic, antiviral, anticancer, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, radioprotective, anti-allergic, anticryptosporidial, and anti-diabetic action are the pharmacological activities of mangiferin. Table No. 2 displays the function of mangiferin and its mode of action.

Antioxidant Activity

Mangiferin and mango leaf extract have been shown in numerous studies to possess strong antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties, and their antioxidant potential is noticeably increased in pro-inflammatory and inflammatory circumstances, such as infections and diabetic states.[36,37]

In an osteoblast-like culture of MC3T3-E1 cells, Xia et al. looked into the protective capacity of mangiferin in a molecular model of H₂O₂-induced oxidative damage.[38] In the MC3T3-E1 cells, mangiferin dramatically decreased oxidative stress and H₂O₂-induced apoptosis. The study showed that mangiferin can prevent oxidative damage in these cultured MC3T3-E1 cells by modifying ERK5/Nrf2 signalling. These findings imply that mangiferin may be a possible treatment or preventative measure for osteoporosis.[38]

Mango stem bark extract has been shown in studies to be effective in preventing the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and it was more effective than vitamins C, E, and β -carotene in reducing their oxidative tissue damage in vivo.[39,40] Mangiferin was therefore investigated for its potential antioxidant benefits both in vitro and in vivo.

Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Mangiferin exerts anti-inflammatory potential in diverse models, according to a number of studies. Mangiferin's ability to prevent doxorubicin (DOX)-induced cardiotoxicity and inflammatory reactions in rats was demonstrated by Agustini et al.[41] Mangiferin demonstrated protection against DOX-induced cardiac apoptosis and inflammation through elevation of SERCA2a gene expression, normalisation of cytosolic calcium levels, and downregulation of pro-apoptotic and pro-inflammatory gene expression.[41]

Wang et al. demonstrated that mangiferin protected against renal ischemia-reperfusion injury by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation in a mouse model and increasing the synthesis of adenosine.[42]

Mangiferin increased adenosine synthesis, enhanced kidney function, elevated CD73 expression in kidneys with ischemia-reperfusion injury, and reduced pro-inflammatory reactions and tubular apoptosis.[42]

In other research, mangiferin inhibits tumour necrosis factor (TNF)-induced NF-kappaB activation and NF-kappaB-dependent genes such ICAM1 (Intercellular Adhesion Molecule 1) and COX2, resulting in an increase in intracellular GSH levels and demonstrating its effectiveness as an anti-inflammatory drug.[43,44]

Gastroprotective Activity

Mangiferin, a naturally occurring glucosyl xanthone from *Mangifera indica*, was tested in mice for its ability to prevent stomach injury brought on by ethanol and indomethacin in the hunt for new gastroprotective drugs. By measuring changes in the mean gastric lesion area or ulcer score in mice and in the stomach secretory volume and total acidity in 4-hour pylorus-ligated rats, the effects of mangiferin on gastric mucosal damage were evaluated.[45] These results show that mangiferin protects against stomach injury brought on by ethanol and indomethacin, possibly through antisecretory and antioxidant mechanisms.

Antimicrobial Activity

Against particular periodontal infections including *Prevotella intermedia* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, mangiferin has antibacterial action in vivo.[46] *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella agona*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Thermoascus aurantiacus*, *Trichoderma reesei*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were among the bacterial and fungal species that the mangiferin solution in polyethylene glycol-400 was found to exert superior activity against. The species most sensitive to it was *Bacillus pumilus*, and it was more efficient against Gram-positive bacteria. *Salmonella agona* was the Gram-negative bacteria that were most susceptible to mangiferin. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* did not exhibit any action in mangiferin.[47]

Analgesic and Antipyretic Activity

Mangiferin's analgesic action was examined by inducing writhing in mice with acetic acid at three dose levels: 0.42, 4.2, and 42.2 i.p. Significant ($P = 0.05$) and dose-dependent activity was seen. A hot plate test verified mangiferin's analgesic effects. Studies on the mechanism suggested that opioid receptors were involved.[48]

Antiviral Activity

Mangiferin and iso mangiferin's antiviral activity against HSV-I, type I herpes simplex virus, was investigated. Isomangiferin's impact was slightly greater than that of acyclovir, idoxuridine, and cyclo cytidinee as control medications. Mangiferin and iso mangiferin had average plaque reduction rates of 56.8% and 69.5%, respectively. Mangiferin and isomangiferin's antiviral effects were probably brought about by their capacity to prevent virus reproduction inside of cells. A subsequent study[49] evaluated the effectiveness of mangiferin against herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2) in vitro. The viral replicative yields were reduced by 90% (EC90) and 99% (EC99) at the concentrations of 33 and 80 g/ml, respectively. Its 50% effective concentration against HSV-2 plaque formation in HeLa cells was 111.7 g/ml. (IC50/EC50) The therapeutic index was 8.1. HSV-2 was not immediately inactivated by mangiferin. Mangiferin may suppress the late event in HSV-2 replication, according to the results of medication addition and removal studies.

Anticancer Activity

Mangiferin inhibits the cytopathic effect of HIV in vitro and increases lymphocyte and macrophage cytotoxicity against tumour cells.[50] Other chemopreventive drugs such 1-acetoxy chavicol acetate have slightly comparable actions. Mangiferin was therefore investigated for its potential anticancer effects both in vitro and in vivo. Tetrazolium salt (MTT) was used to assess the anti-proliferation effects of mangiferin on K562 leukaemia cells[51].

Cardioprotective Activity

On experimentally generated cardiotoxic myocardial infarcted rats, mangiferin has cardioprotective and hypolipidemic effects.[52] According to current research, mangiferin's ability to reduce oxidative damage and activate mitochondrial energy metabolism is what gives it its protective properties.[53]

Neuroprotective Activity

Mangiferin is neuroprotective in both in vitro and in vivo forms of ischemia, according to Gottlieb et al.[54] In the presence of submicromolar concentrations of mangiferin, cell death brought on by glutamate in neuronal cells was reduced, which in turn suppressed receptor-mediated calcium influx, oxidative stress, and apoptosis. Additionally, when given to rats after the injury, it reduced the production of free radicals and neuronal death in the hippocampal CA1 region brought on by transient forebrain ischemia. Importantly, treated-ischemic rats performed much better in three hippocampal-dependent behavioural tasks, indicating that the neuroprotection provided by this antioxidant was functionally useful. These findings collectively suggest that mangiferin has strong neuroprotective properties that may have therapeutic relevance in the treatment of acute brain injury and impairment.[54]

Radioprotective Activity

The radioprotective effect of various mangiferin concentrations was also investigated in the whole body of DBAxC57BL mice exposed to 10 Gy of -irradiation.[55] When compared to the unmedicated irradiated controls, the treatment of mice with various dosages of mangiferin one hour before to radiation reduced the signs of radiation illness and postponed the beginning of mortality. Mangiferin's radioprotective effects grew dose-dependently up to 2 mg/kg before diminishing after that. The maximum number of animals survived the radiation-induced mortality at 2 mg/kg mangiferin, which had the highest radioprotective efficacy.

Antiallergic Activity

As measured by the passive cutaneous anaphylaxis test (sensitization with infected mouse serum with a high IgE titre, followed by stimulation with the cytosolic fraction of *T. spiralis* muscle larvae), rats were given mangiferin (50 mg/kg body weight/day) orally for 50 days. Since IgE is essential for the development of allergic disorders.[56] In a recent study, mangiferin demonstrated significant dose-dependent inhibition of histamine-induced vascular permeability, histamine release induced by compound 48/80 from rat mast cells, and lymphocyte proliferative response as evidence of the reduction in the amount of B and T lymphocytes able to contribute to the allergic response.[57]

Anticryptosporidial Activity

In a neonatal mouse model, the inhibitory activity of mangiferin (50 mg/kg/die and 100 mg/kg/die) was assessed, and its activity was compared with that of paromomycin (100 mg/kg/die). Mangiferin exhibits strong anticryptosporidial efficacy at 100 mg/kg, and its activity is comparable to that of paromomycin at the same dose (100 mg/kg). Mangiferin and paromomycin, however, were only able to partially suppress the intestinal colonisation of *C. parvum*. In comparison to the untreated control, this reduction was estimated to be above 80% for both mangiferin and paromomycin. Only after the course of treatment was complete was significant action for mangiferin at 50 mg/kg discovered.[58]

Antidiabetic Activity

Mangiferin significantly lowers hyperlipidemia in type 2 diabetes and has considerable antidiabetic action.[59] Mangiferin also lowered blood glucose levels in KK-Ay mice during an insulin tolerance test and alleviated hyperinsulinemia. Based on these results, it appears plausible that mangiferin reduces insulin resistance in order to exhibit its antidiabetic activity.[59,60] An animal model of non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) called KK-Ay mice was used to assess the antidiabetic effect of mangiferin. Following oral dosing, mangiferin reduced the blood glucose level in KK-Ay mice. The fact that normal mice showed no change in blood glucose levels suggests that MF is effective in treating NIDDM.[61] Mangiferin is an excellent treatment for diabetes mellitus type 2 (T2DM) because it dramatically suppresses protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B, an inhibitor of the insulin signalling pathway.[62] Additionally, it promotes the absorption of glucose from the intestine, which aids in the lowering of triglycerides, cholesterol, and LDL-cholesterol, while inhibiting some enzymes like the glucoside enzyme, isomaltase, maltase, and enzyme sucrose.[63] Preclinical investigations further demonstrate that it increases insulin sensitivity by facilitating glucose utilisation in oxidative metabolism by activating the mammalian dehydrogenase complex.[64-66]

Mangiferin was found to have a significant anti-diabetic effect in a study by Sellamuthu et al. This was most likely because it stimulated insulin secretion and action from remaining pancreatic β -cells, which improved glucose uptake and metabolism in peripheral tissues of experimentally infected diabetic rats.

Table No:2. Various roles of mangiferin mechanism of action.

Role of mangiferin	Mechanism of action	References
Antioxidant	↑antioxidant enzymes like Catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx).	[67-69]
Anti-inflammatory	Causes inhibition of interleukin (IL)-1 receptor-associated kinase 1 (IRAK1), NF- κ B and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) phosphorylation via LPS.	[69,70]
Cardioprotective	↓Serum and heart level of cholesterol, triglycerides, and free fatty acid and ↑heart tissue phospholipid levels	[69, 71]
Immunomodulatory	Inhibits IgE production, anaphylaxis reaction, histamine-induced vascular permeability, and histamine release and lymphocyte proliferative response.	[72, 73]
Anticancer	It arrests the cell cycle in the G2/M phase via ATR-Chk1 DNA damage stressresponse pathways.	[69, 74]
Antidiabetic	↑Pancreatic β cell mass and amount of glucose and insulin uptake along with increased phosphorylation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK).	[69, 70, 75]

CONCLUSION

Mangiferin is a herbal drug that needs to be explored for its potent therapeutic activity. Mangiferin belongs to a polyphenolic compound with xanthone moiety in its ring. The polyphenolic groups present in the structure are responsible for wide activities. Mangiferin has extensive pharmacological activities like anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant effect, anticancer etc. A C-glucosidexanthone derived from mango, mangiferin, it is a strong natural medication with a variety of pharmacological effects. Numerous illnesses, including cardiovascular problems, inflammation, different types of cancer, neurological problems, and diabetes, can be helped by it.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

MGF – mangiferin

DMSO – dimethyl sulfoxide

DMF – dimethyl formamide

DOX – doxorubicin

ROS – reactive oxidative species

TNF – tumor necrosis factor

LDL – low density lipoprotein

DM – diabetes mellitus

NIDDM – non-insulin-dependent-diabetes mellitus

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